

IP4OS

D4.1 Synergy Core Curriculum

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Key takeaway messages

- The Synergy Core Curriculum provides a structured framework for integrating Intellectual Property and Open Science.
- The ADDIE instructional model ensures systematic training design, implementation, and evaluation.
- The Pilot Learning Lab strengthens institutional capacity for knowledge valorisation across Europe and establishes multi-professional consultation teams across Europe, enabling cross-sectoral collaboration and institutional change.
- Open Educational Resources ensure the sustainability and scalability of training activities.

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the development of the **Synergy Core Curriculum** and the implementation of the training programme **IP4OS Pilot Learning Lab**, supporting capacity building for **Knowledge Valorisation in Europe**. The objective of IP4OS is to strengthen institutional and individual capacity for Knowledge Valorisation in Europe by integrating Intellectual Property (IP) and Open Science (OS) competencies through a structured curriculum and participatory training programme within European Research Performing Organisations (RPO).

To achieve this objective, the project developed the ‘Synergy Core Curriculum’ and implemented a multi-level training programme, ‘IP4OS Pilot Learning Lab’. The methodology combined curriculum design based on FAIR-by-Design principles, didactical framework grounded in multi-professional and cross-department collaboration, and the ADDIE (Analyse, Design, Develop, Implement, Evaluate) instructional design model, ensuring systematic training development, delivery, and evaluation. Implementing training through profession-specific modules, Open Educational Resources (OERs), and the Pilot Learning Lab was ensured by the Europe-wide establishment of multi-professional teams participating in collaborative learning environments and testing institutional procedures for IP–OS integration.

The IP4OS Pilot Learning Lab constitutes the project’s Train-the-Trainer scheme. Within IP4OS, the Pilot Learning Lab (PLL) is not an additional training format but the structured mechanism through which multi-professional teams are qualified as institutional multipliers. By participating in the three-session, action-oriented learning sprint and conducting guided field tests between sessions, participants develop the competences required to replicate the IP–OS approach within their institutions. The PLL therefore fulfils the Train-the-Trainer function foreseen in WP4: it equips members of multi-professional teams to deliver consultations, facilitate dialogue across professional silos, apply the Synergy Framework in practice, and embed knowledge valorisation routines into institutional procedures. Through reusable templates, structured facilitation guidance, and evaluation tools, the PLL ensures scalability and transferability beyond the project duration.

Results include the

- successful development of the **Synergy Core Curriculum** structured across macro, meso, and micro levels to ensure alignment between institutional strategy, learning design, and practical implementation and supported by the validation of the didactical concept for multi-professional teams, emphasising dialogue, experimentation, and institutional integration in the training programme (see M6);
- **Profession-Deepening Modules** for [Librarians](#), Knowledge Technology Transfer Professionals (in prep.), Data Stewards (in prep.), and Research Managers(in prep.);
- **IP4OS Pilot Learning Labs** serve as experiential learning labs, enhancing participants' knowledge, skills, awareness, and advocacy, and institutional readiness for knowledge valorisation and fostering cross-sectoral collaboration and institutional change.
- **IP4OS Toolbox** consisting of supporting materials and guides such as [Knowledge Valorisation Rubric](#), [FAIR-R²L Rubric](#), [Valorisation Consultancy Form](#), [Concepts, Valorisation Pathway, and Resources for IP and OS](#), [Guide on Multi-professional Teams and Consultations](#), [Pilot Learning Lab](#)

The programme was approved by the consortium and prepared for dissemination as OER, ensuring scalability and sustainability.

In conclusion, the project successfully developed and validated a structured capacity-building framework for knowledge valorisation, enhancing Europe's innovation ecosystem. The curriculum provides a scalable and sustainable framework for embedding IP and OS integration into European research institutions. Future work will focus on engaging a Community of Practice, empowering national multipliers, and embedding the curriculum and Pilot Learning Labs into institutional and European training infrastructures.

List of abbreviations

ADDIE	Analyse, Design, Develop, Implement, Evaluate
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CoP	Community of Practice
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IA	Intellectual Asset
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
IP4OS	Intellectual Property for Open Science (Horizon Europe project)
KTO	Knowledge and Technology Transfer Officer
OER	Open Educational Resources
OIC	Open Innovation Challenge
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
TTO	Technology Transfer Officer

1. Guide to Build Capacity for Knowledge Valorisation in Europe

1.1 Conceptual Foundations to Knowledge Valorisation and Capacity Building by IP4OS

Knowledge valorisation refers to the process of generating social, economic, and environmental value by transforming research results into solutions that benefit society, the economy and support innovation ecosystems (1). It is a cornerstone of Europe's research and innovation (R&I) policy, aiming to strengthen competitiveness, sustainable growth, and responsible innovation and relies on the complementary interaction between Intellectual Property (IP) and Open Science (OS), which together enable both protection and dissemination of research outputs.

Europe can support knowledge valorisation through various structural policies and actions (ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024 and 2025-2027). A crucial aspect is **capacity building in IP and OS** (2). Both IP and OS are key enablers of knowledge valorisation: IP frameworks enable institutions and researchers to protect, share, transfer, and transform intellectual assets into innovation by safeguarding results, strategically managing their reuse, ensuring legal protection, and facilitating commercialisation. Conversely, OS maximises transparency, accessibility, reproducibility, and reuse of research outputs—aligned with FAIR principles—to enhance visibility, traceability, reproducibility, and the advancement of knowledge. Together, in a fitting interplay, they allow Europe to derive economic, environmental and societal value from its research investments. The integration of IP and OS supports a balanced approach described as “as open as possible, as closed as necessary,” allowing research outputs to be widely accessible to achieve maximum societal, environmental and economic impact while preserving necessary protections.

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"I think we have to educate people in IP and OS, we have to educate researchers, but also support mechanisms that researchers have around them." — Frantzeska Papadopoulou, Professor of Intellectual Property Law, Stockholm University

Box 1. Knowledge Valorisation Key Concepts

Knowledge Valorisation “[...] is the process of creating social, [environmental] and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors and transforming [research outputs (results, data, software, code, etc.)] into sustainable products, services, solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society.”(3)

Open Science, as defined by UNESCO, is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefit of scientists and society as a whole. Open Science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable.

“As open as possible, as closed as necessary” This principle is a key tenet of Open Science, advocating for sharing knowledge without unnecessary or inappropriate barriers.

“Open” in this framework refers to approaches that use no or low degrees of restrictiveness. In the case of data, it is associated with FAIR principles, while in that of copyright, with licences such as CC-BY and CC-BY-SA. It is seen as facilitating further research and downstream innovation.

FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) support research outputs to be machine-actionable and therefore foster sharing, redistribution, and reproduction.

FAIR-R²L

FAIR-expansion (as focusing on technical aspects and machine-actionability) to FAIR plus ‘Responsibly Licensed’, adding the requirement to datasets being responsibly licensed and legally ready for reuse (whether in research or machine learning workflows or in use by AI). (4)

Intellectual Asset (IA): “[R]esults or products generated through R&I activities” (5) (such as data, software, publications, inventions, or know-how) that have scientific, societal, or economic value in their own right. Some of these intellectual assets may be protected through Intellectual Property Rights; where this occurs, the resulting rights constitute additional, legally enforceable assets that can support valorisation and exploitation.

Intellectual Property (IP) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR): “The result of intellectual activities that is eligible for legal protection and includes inventions, literary and artistic works, symbols, names, images, and designs.” (6)
IP4OS concentrates especially on the management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in ways that are compatible with Open Science, such as decisions concerning copyright, open-source licensing, regulatory exclusivity, etc.

However, current European research environments face challenges in integrating IP and OS practices effectively. While awareness of OS is widespread, many stakeholders lack the confidence and training required to apply IP and OS strategically. Institutional guidance is often fragmented, and incentives do not consistently support knowledge valorisation practices. Sharma et al. 2025 (7) describe for the first time the following current status quo on knowledge valorisation perception in Europe:

- Stakeholders across Europe widely recognise that IP and OS can be complementary, but in practice, they are often handled in parallel rather than together.
- While 56% of interviewed participants report high familiarity with OS, only 11.9% feel confident using IP and OS in favour of reciprocal benefits.
- Current barriers include a lack of clear institutional guidance, limited awareness of open licensing mechanisms, and legal differences between EU member states.
- Misaligned goals in collaborations, licensing complexities, and insufficient training persist as persistent obstacles.

What is missing to foster knowledge valorisation (see the [Synergy Framework](#)):

- Training and capacity building: Researchers and managers call for targeted training on open licensing tools and practical considerations
- Policy and institutional support: Few universities have clear frameworks that integrate IP and OS, leading to uncertainty and conflicts for those without clear guidance.
- Incentives: Current career systems reward patents and publications, but OS contributions are not consistently recognised.

These gaps highlight the need for structured training and institutional capacity building focusing on a synergistic application of IP management and OS practices, called the concerted IP-OS approach, as promoted by IP4OS.

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"By addressing those barriers between IP and OS, I think we can further advance open science in Europe and in the world." — Gustav Nilsson, Associate Professor of Neuroscience, Karolinska Institutet

1.2 IP4OS's empowerment pathways to support a proficient European Community of Practice for innovative Valorisation strategies

To achieve this, the IP4OS project implemented a three-step capacity-building process.

1.2.1 Preparing the Curriculum Knowledge Base: Synergy Framework

The first phase, coordinated by the Karolinska Institutet within WP2, established a theoretical knowledge framework using a rigorous three-strand methodological approach. Through a scoping review, stakeholder survey, and expert engagement, robust insights were developed on managing IP and OS, as well as the potential of a **concerted IP-OS approach**. This knowledge was consolidated in the [Synergy Framework](#) (7), a **manual** supplementing the [Code of Practice on the management of intellectual assets for knowledge valorisation in the European Research Area](#) and designed to support the concerted IP–OS approach, pushing back against the idea that openness and IP protection are inherently at odds, and putting into practice the principle of being “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” in order to unpack effective valorisation possibilities for economic growth, societal and environmental progress, or improved policy making. The framework offers evidence-informed recommendations to help researchers and institutions tackle common challenges. It recommends tools and practices to help multi-professional teams integrate IP protection with sharing and reuse, while emphasising the need for strong institutional support and continuous training on copyright, (open) licensing, and data governance. This equips stakeholders with the necessary expertise throughout the research lifecycle.

1.2.2 Synergy Core Curriculum

During the course of the IP4OS project, award-winning education experts at Kiel University (CAU), supported by the University of Zagreb School of Medicine (UZSM), transferred this knowledge into an innovative [Synergy Core Curriculum](#) accompanied by **learner-focused and openly accessible materials** (see section 2.2) for pre-defined target groups (see table 1). These materials are designed for (A) *IP Experts and Intermediaries*, (B) Experts Performing Research, and (C) Trainers teaching IP to multi-professional teams supporting the content of the Synergy Core Curriculum. The openly accessible materials showcase different topics and roles in which IP can ideally boost OS. A well-designed, easy-to-understand description with examples and didactical tips.

The didactically innovative curriculum is grounded in mutual and dialogue-based learning, knowledge sharing across roles, and the collaborative, cross-sectoral development of valorisation strategies.

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"So I do think capacity building is the only way, actually, to support this field and to bring relation and dissemination of knowledge, in a really broad sense, into the European research area." — Julia Priess-Buchheit, Professor, Kiel University

1.2.3 IP4OS Learning Labs

This work established the theoretical and practical groundwork for implementation in training contexts. The curriculum and materials are currently being implemented in the IP4OS Training Centre's [Pilot Learning Labs](#), conceptualised and led by EURICE (see section 2.3). The goal is the establishment and training of **multi-professional teams** in RPOs of all European Member States and 300 **individuals**.

IP4OS's Synergy Core Curriculum and the Pilot Learning Lab support a Europe-wide formation of multi-professional teams providing consultations to valorisation strategies with the objective of maximising the effectiveness of the concerted IP-OS approach. These **trained teams and individuals create a European Community of Practice which is empowered to apply innovative and future-oriented valorisation strategies within its RPOs and research projects.**

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"There is a great need for people to understand what a patent is, its limitations, its advantages, but also the other forms of intellectual property." — Richard Gold, Professor of Law, McGill University

1.3 Target Groups and Capacity Building Needs

The Synergy Core Curriculum addresses three primary target groups essential to knowledge valorisation:

IP Experts and Intermediaries (Group A)

This group provides institutional support by advising researchers on IP protection, licensing, compliance, and data management. Its role is essential for facilitating knowledge transfer and ensuring alignment between legal requirements and OS principles.

Experts performing research (in need of IA management for their work/projects) (Group B)

This group consists of primary creators of IA and must make decisions regarding protection, dissemination, and reuse. Its responsibilities include managing IAs responsibly, balancing publication priorities with protection strategies, and complying with institutional and funding requirements. Training enables this group to maximise the impact and visibility of its work.

Trainers in IP or Research (Group C)

Trainers serve as institutional multipliers who embed knowledge valorisation practices into educational and organisational structures. They translate policies into practical learning opportunities and promote sustainable cultural change within research institutions.

Representatives of these groups form a multi-professional ecosystem required to support sustainable knowledge valorisation across institutions.

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"I think what makes my work particularly meaningful and interesting to me is to be able to support people, to make their own decisions, to make informed decisions, and to look at what can be quite a technical area of the law or a very complex series of processes and procedures and be able to navigate their way through in order to achieve the outcomes that they really want to." — Chris Morrison, Bodleian Libraries, University of Oxford

The following table shows all 15 target groups defined by IP4OS (subsumed into three main groups: A, B, and C) and targeted by the training:

Table 1: IP4OS target groups

Target Group	Sub-group	No.	Representatives	Level of awareness, skills, advocacy for		
Group A. IP experts and intermediaries		1	KTT Professionals	X X X		
		2	Infrastructure providing stakeholders in the EU R&I system (e.g. RFOs, RPOs, Publishers, Companies working on science communication & dissemination in EU projects)	X X X		
		3	Entrepreneurship Officers	X X		
		4	Research Librarians	X X X		
		5	Data Managers / Data Stewards	X X		
		6	Research Managers	X X		
		7	Policymakers (as promoters and supporters of scientific messages and tools)	X		
Group B. Experts performing research (in need of IA management for their work/projects)	B1 active in the public sector	8	OS Ambassadors	X X X		
		9	Researchers*	X		
		10	Research students**	X		
		11	Academic and University lecturers	X		
		12	Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs (collaborating with public sector)	XX		
		13	RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff	X X		
		3	Entrepreneurship Officers	X X		
	B2 active in the private sector	8	OS Ambassadors	X X X		
		13	RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff	X X		
		12	Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs	X X		
		14	Innovators from Spin-Offs and Start-Ups	X X		
		9	Researchers*	XX		
		Group C. Trainers in IP or research		1	KTT Professionals	X X X
				8	OS Ambassadors	X X X
15	Teaching Librarians			X X X		
13	RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff			XX		
3	Entrepreneurship Officers			XX		
11	Academic and University lecturers			X		

* Researchers at all stages of their careers in different fields.

** BA-, MA-, PhD candidates

X These persons have low awareness either in OS or in IA management.

XX These persons have some awareness, but low skills either in OS or in IA management.

XXX These persons have some awareness and skills, but never advocated OS or in IA management in their community.

1.4 Curriculum Objectives and Learning Outcomes

The curriculum is designed to achieve four overarching learning objectives:

Knowledge:

Participants develop an understanding of IP and OS frameworks, licensing mechanisms (e.g., FAIR principles, open licensing), and knowledge valorisation strategies.

Skills:

Participants acquire practical competencies in managing IAs, apply tools (e.g., data management plans), select appropriate licenses, and implement knowledge sharing strategies.

Awareness:

Participants learn to recognise situations requiring careful IP–OS balance, including legal sensitivities, collaboration agreements, and ethical considerations.

Advocacy:

Participants gain the ability to promote knowledge valorisation practices through balanced IP-OS approaches within their institutions and professional communities.

These objectives ensure that participants not only understand knowledge valorisation but also apply it effectively in practice.

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"Since it's part of it, not addressing it is going to end up stifling the innovation that open science can kind of uncover." — Tim Errington, Center for Open Science

1.5 The ADDIE Didactical Model for Knowledge Valorisation Training

The capacity building programme applies the ADDIE instructional design model, consisting of five phases: Analyse, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate. This model ensures systematic and effective development of training programmes.

- **Analyse:** In this phase, trainers identify target groups, assess participants' needs, and examine real-world research scenarios.
- **Design:** Learning objectives, training sessions, and expected outcomes are defined. Training modules are selected and aligned with specific learning goals such as awareness, skills development, and advocacy.
- **Develop:** Training materials are created or adapted using OERs and other resources, including case studies, exercises, and instructional materials. This phase ensures that training content is relevant and accessible.
- **Implement:** Training sessions are delivered through interactive, collaborative formats, including team-oriented and scenario-based exercises and group discussions. These activities simulate real institutional environments and support experiential learning.
- **Evaluate:** Participant feedback and learning outcomes are assessed to ensure refinement and sustainability of the training programme.

By applying ADDIE, the project established a structured and scalable framework for institutional capacity building, transforming knowledge valorisation training into a sustainable organisational practice rather than isolated training events.

1.6 Concept of the Synergy Core Curriculum

The Synergy Core Curriculum provides a comprehensive framework for training and institutional capacity building, structured across three interconnected levels:

- **Macro Level:** The macro level focuses on identifying institutional and target group needs through needs assessments, outreach strategies, and programme planning. This ensures alignment between institutional priorities and training activities.
- **Meso Level:** At the meso level, learning programmes are designed and organisational prerequisites are established. This includes selecting instructors, designing training methods, preparing learning materials, and organising logistical aspects such as schedules and delivery formats.
- **Micro Level:** The micro level focuses on the implementation, delivery, and evaluation of training activities. Participants actively engage in learning processes, co-create solutions, and contribute to institutional change.

This multi-level approach ensures coherence between strategic planning and operational implementation.

2. Application of the Synergy Core Curriculum and Pilot Learning Lab

2.1 Multi-Professional Consulting Teams

A concerted IP-OS approach to knowledge valorisation is underpinned by **multi-professional consulting teams**, which bring together expertise in both OS and IP. Based on the Synergy Core Curriculum, IP4OS establishes and trains [multi-professional teams](#) across all 27 European Member States and 300 individuals in its Pilot Learning Labs, thus forming a Community of Practice that acts as multipliers of the acquired knowledge.

These teams bring together IP experts and KTO/TTOs, OS Ambassadors, librarians, data stewards and research managers working hand in hand with researchers to systematically develop tailored knowledge valorisation strategies for their research projects. In consultations, they help researchers identify emerging IAs, clarify strategic objectives, and assess whether IP is necessary and/or beneficial to a project. When IP is favourable, these teams help identify the most suitable IP right (IPR) that fulfils the business purpose or other valorisation strategy and promotes maximum openness and utilisation of the IA. Through structured dialogue and collaborative decision-making, the multi-professional teams enhance institutional capacity and support a culture change towards sustainable knowledge valorisation practices, leveraging IP and OS.

2.2 Supplementary Materials to Knowledge Valorisation developed by IP4OS

The curriculum and training are supported by a variety of structured frameworks, additional tools and resources to Knowledge Valorisation, including:

1. Synergy Framework

The Synergy Framework is an openly accessible manual supplementing the [Code of Practice on the management of intellectual assets for knowledge valorisation in the European Research Area](#) and offers evidence-informed recommendations to help researchers and institutions tackle common challenges and apply a concerted IP-OS approach to value creation (8).

2. [Knowledge Valorisation Rubric](#) is a guide distinguishing three dimensions and providing practical guidance for making strategic decisions that maximise both openness and protection (9).

- **Focus of IA use:**
Distinguishing between creating new IAs and reusing existing IAs, and applying appropriate IP and licensing strategies accordingly.
- **Level of Reuse:**
Selecting appropriate licensing and openness levels based on intended reuse and strategic goals.
- **Time:**
Determining when intellectual property protection or sharing should occur and for how long.

FAIR-R²L: IP4OS (developed by Miller International Knowledge) adds a further crucial dimension: datasets must also be *Responsibly Licensed*, ethically sound, in line with the PID strategy, sustainable and legally ready for reuse in AI and machine learning workflows ([source](#)).

RESPONSIBLE LICENSING CONCEPT REQUIRES

- | | |
|--|--|
| <p>requires:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licence must be included with the dataset • Machine-readable exposure (SPDX, schema.org) • Needs to explicitly allow AI training & derivatives • Avoid NC/ND for AI reuse • Attribute rights clearly | <p>adds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explicit dual-format licensing • AI-specific suitability & documentation • Ethics & GDPR lane • Collection- vs item-level clarity • PID lineage across splits and models • Long-term stewardship commitment |
|--|--|

3. FAIR-R²L Rubric is a tool that supports actors in ensuring and/or assessing the **FAIR** principles (10), **AI-Readiness (FAIR-R; 11)**, and **Responsible Licensing (FAIR-R²L; 12)** of their datasets or those they intend to reuse.

4. Knowledge Valorisation Pathway visualising a four-step process of valorisation under a common IP-OS umbrella (13).

Further strategic guidance to consultations and multi-professional teams supports the establishment and workflows of these consultancy bodies within institutions:

5. Valorisation Consultancy Form enabling researchers to register a consultation on a concerted IP-OS approach. These forms will be implemented into the institutional websites and promoted in order to stimulate researchers to call upon a multi-professional team of their organisation. Via the form, researchers provide initial information to their project and intentions to IP-application and/or openness. Based on this information, the multi-professional team convenes and collaboratively develops individual valorisation strategies under IP-OS together with the researcher (14).

VALORISATION CONSULTANCY FORM		IP4OS	
<p>Defining the Intended Research Impact and Valorisation Pathways, Intellectual Assets, Intellectual Property Rights and Licenses</p> <p>Effectively managing research outputs and assets is crucial for maximising the research's excellence, impact, valorisation and visibility.</p> <p>In the following tables you can provide initial information on your intentions for the use of your intellectual assets. Note that each intellectual asset has to be listed separately (start filling for a further intellectual asset after STEP 4.)</p> <p>Provide as much information as possible; the team will help fill any gaps.</p>			
<p>STEP 1 - What are your research goals, values and intended impact to be achieved?</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>			
<p>STEP 2 - Role focus: Identifying intellectual assets Identify and list all intellectual assets (research artefacts and results) expected from your project for which you seek consultation on usage rights. Guiding question: Which intellectual Property tools ensure fit-for-purpose practice?</p>			
<p>2.1 Producing new intellectual assets Determine if you are producing new outputs. Guiding question: Which intellectual Property tools ensure fit-for-purpose practice?</p>		<p>2.2 Reusing existing intellectual assets Determine what existing outputs you aim to reuse. Guiding question: Which licences apply, and under what conditions?</p>	
<p>Name the intellectual asset you will produce (Note: Name each asset separately. Start with the first asset, complete STEPS 3 and 4, then proceed to the next asset.)</p> <p><i>-Free text: new intellectual asset-</i></p>	<p>Select the Intended Intellectual Property Right or Licence Note: For Trade Secrets & Know-How no reusability specification applicable</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness • Copyright • Trademark/Trade Name • Plant Variety Right • Industrial Design & Aesthetic Innovation • Creative Commons Licences • Local/All-Licence agreements • Creative Commons Licences (please specify in the consultation) • Other (please specify in the consultation) 	<p>Name an existing Intellectual asset you will reuse</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>	<p>Name the assigned Intellectual Property Right or Licence</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>
<p>STEP 3 - Level of reuse Determine the output's openness. Guiding question: Which licence or access mechanism fits best, and under what conditions?</p> <p><i>-Openness-</i> Limited Medium High</p>		<p>STEP 3 - Conditions of reuse Clarify reuse licences, exceptions or limitations and adhere to them. Follow the openness conditions of reused outputs to ensure compliance. Guiding question: Which licences apply, and under what conditions?</p>	
<p>STEP 4 - Timing Determine when to apply Intellectual Property Rights or Licences (before disclosure, before publication, or after FAIR sharing). Guiding question: Which Intellectual Property tools at this stage best preserve future options and enable responsible sharing?</p>		<p>STEP 4 - Timing Reuse according to the licence/ law/exception/other provision.</p>	
<p>Start date</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>	<p>For how long?</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>	<p>Start date</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>	<p>For how long?</p> <p><i>-Free text-</i></p>

6. A compilation of [Guide on Multi-professional Teams and Consultations](#), consisting of the **Guide to Establishing Multi-professional Teams for Research Knowledge Valorisation**, experiences of the **First pilot of a Multi-professional Team**, and the **Guide for Consultations** supporting multi-professional teams to deliver effective consultations on valorisation strategies (15).

7. [Pilot Learning Lab](#) outlining the process of the multi-professional teams' training to be delivered between January and July 2026 (16).

8. [Glossary of Concepts and Terms and Micro-Level Library](#) presenting additional literature to IP and OS (13).

9. Profession-Specific Deepening Modules

Furthermore, the Synergy Core Curriculum is accompanied by **four profession-deepening modules** that provide insights into the working realities of the professional roles forming a multi-professional team: [Librarians](#) (17), KTO/TOs (in prep.), Data Stewards (in prep.), and Research Managers (in prep.); all modules will be findable in the [Zenodo IP4OS community](#). The goal of these modules is to empower European professionals to act as advisors and advocates in OS implementation — capable of integrating IP awareness, agile rights management, and open practices to ensure compliant, ethical, and impactful knowledge valorisation.

These modules use interactive learning methods such as a fishbowl format, including expert panel discussions as the inner circle of the fishbowl, followed by scenario-based exercises, and reflection tools as an outer or subsequent learning setting, enabling reflection on knowledge acquired. Great importance was given to the selection of experts in terms of both local and gender distribution. At the same time, the experts fulfil the **role models'** function as described in T3.1, advocating for a concerted IP-OS approach. By demonstrating real-world

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situations, institutional integration, policy or workflow developments, as well as cross-role collaborations, these modules are aimed at highlighting the IP-OS Synergy in action, emphasising empowerment and responsibility. They support self-paced learning while reinforcing collaborative capacity building.

These supplementary materials support a comprehensive understanding of Knowledge Valorisation under a concerted IP-OS approach and offer practical guidance to institutional integration and long-term sustainability of knowledge valorisation practices.

2.3 Pilot Learning Lab

2.3.1 Participatory Training Concept for Multi-Professional Teams in the Pilot Learning Lab

The training programme of the [Pilot Learning Lab](#) (16) is based on an innovative didactical concept designed to foster collaboration between professionals with diverse expertise.

The concept combines self-paced learning modules with interactive learning environments such as Pilot Learning Labs. Participants engage in dialogue-based learning, role-based exercises, and collaborative reflection to develop shared understanding and institutional strategies.

This approach ensures that knowledge valorisation becomes an institutional practice supported by collaboration rather than an individual responsibility.

2.3.2 The Pilot Learning Lab as the IP4OS Train-the-Trainer Programme

The Pilot Learning Lab (PLL) operationalises the Train-the-Trainer concept of IP4OS. While the Synergy Core Curriculum provides the conceptual and didactical foundation, the PLL translates this foundation into institutional practice by qualifying participants as multipliers within their Research Performing Organisations (RPOs).

In contrast to traditional Train-the-Trainer formats that focus primarily on content transmission, the PLL follows a team-based empowerment logic. Participants do not merely acquire knowledge about IP and Open Science; they learn to facilitate cross-role dialogue, structure consultancy processes, and co-develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) tailored to their institutional context.

The Train-the-Trainer function of the PLL is achieved through four core components:

1. **Structured Facilitation Design** – Each of the three sessions follows a reproducible format (orientation, experimentation, transfer), enabling participants to replicate the structure independently.
2. **Experiential Field Testing** – Between sessions, teams conduct real-life mini-experiments within their institution, strengthening their capacity to apply and adapt the IP–OS approach.
3. **Reusable Implementation Tools** – Templates (e.g., KV Consultancy form, KV Pathway, Guides) and reflection instruments support transferability.
4. **Embedded Evaluation Logic (ADDIE – Evaluate)** – Feedback loops and micro-reporting foster continuous refinement and professionalisation of consultation practices.

Through this design, the Pilot Learning Lab ensures that trained professionals can act as multipliers, capable of independently implementing and disseminating the concerted IP–OS approach across departments, projects, and national contexts. In this sense, the PLL constitutes the decentralised Training Centre envisioned in WP4 and supports the establishment of a sustainable European Community of Practice.

2.3.3 Structure and Implementation

The Pilot Learning Lab is a strategic implementation sprint designed to establish and strengthen multi-professional teams.

The Lab consists of three structured sessions:

Session 1: Roles, Realities, and Friction Points

Participants identify professional roles, clarify responsibilities, and analyse barriers to effective collaboration.

Session 2: Communication and Collaboration

Participants test collaborative workflows, develop team coordination strategies, and improve communication practices.

Session 3: Transfer and Implementation

Participants reflect on outcomes, develop institutional procedures, and plan the implementation of knowledge valorisation practices.

Between sessions, participants conduct field tests, engage with the profession, deepen modules and apply learned concepts in real institutional contexts.

2.4 Open Innovation Challenge

Alongside the Pilot Learning Labs, IP4OS conceptualises and implements the [Open Innovation Challenge](#) (OIC; Task 3.3, Grant Agreement) during 2026. The OIC is a central element—together with the Europe-wide multi-professional teams established through the Pilot Learning Labs (see 2.3)—in building a European Community of Practice (CoP) applying a concerted IP-OS approach to Research Knowledge Valorisation.

The OIC invites experts from OS, IP, Knowledge Transfer, and related fields, as described in the [multi-professional teams concept](#), as well as experts in the fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI), to form multi-professional teams. Teams already established in the context of the Pilot Learning Labs or new teams are welcome. Their task: develop valorisation strategies for research activities at the intersection of AI, OS, and IP management that generate societal or environmental value, leveraging the interplay of OS and IP concepts. Shortlisted teams receive mentoring and capacity development from IP4OS. Winners are invited to the IP4OS Summit in Brussels (October 2026) and featured on the IP4OS website.

Participants are recruited through the consortium's networks, IP4OS website, project and partner mailing lists, partner events, and social media (see example on [LinkedIn](#)). Additionally, partner MIK will offer 30 further sessions on IP and OS at [IE University](#) from September 2026, embedded in the OIC context.

2.5 Impact and Sustainability of the project's activities

IP4OS's capacity building programme—grounded in the Synergy Core Curriculum and delivered throughout 2026 via the Pilot Learning Labs (see 2.3), the Open Innovation Challenge (see 2.4), and OERs (Profession Deepening Modules and the IP4OS Toolbox)—aims to establish an informed CoP that understands and applies the concerted IP-OS approach to impactful valorisation strategies. IP4OS holds the distinctive advantage of partnering with organisations committed to this approach, not only during but also beyond the project's lifetime. The partners IFLA, ASTP, MIK, EURICE, and USZM have already declared their intent to continue targeted knowledge dissemination of the IP4OS concept for their specific audiences and their needs after the project ends. Specifically, we are happy that MIK will be able to cover all professions from a multi-professional team.

3. Conclusion

The project demonstrates that **structured capacity building** can align IP and OS, enhancing knowledge valorisation. It successfully developed and implemented a comprehensive capacity-building framework for knowledge valorisation in Europe. By developing the openly accessible **Synergy Core Curriculum**, **supplementary resources**, and the **Pilot Learning Lab**, IP4OS builds and trains multi-professional teams across all

European Member States. These efforts drive institutional change and promote methodologies that integrate IP and OS practices.

Expert voice: Why capacity building in knowledge valorisation matters

"I think capacity building is the first step in order to make people see that there is an issue in knowledge valorisation, that there is something that we all have been doing which is maybe not good for us, for us as a society." — Katharina Miller, Research Director, MIK

Key findings so far demonstrate that European institutions understand the benefits of this innovative knowledge valorisation pathway, as well as of institutional multi-professional teams enhancing researchers' ability to manage IAs strategically and collaboratively. In addition to traditional roles like librarianship, research management, and data stewardship, many participating European RPOs had already set up dedicated structures—such as Technology Transfer Centres and Open Science Offices. This further underscored the importance of these professional roles and reinforced the relevance of the IP4OS strategy, which emphasises cross-role collaboration as a foundation for advancing OS practices.

The curriculum's structured design across macro, meso, and micro levels ensures alignment between institutional strategy and practical implementation. The application of the ADDIE instructional model ensures systematic and sustainable training development, delivery, and evaluation.

The Pilot Learning Lab proved particularly effective in fostering institutional change by enabling participants to experiment with collaborative workflows, develop Standard Operating Procedures, and strengthen institutional capacity for Knowledge Valorisation.

The project's significance lies in its contribution to strengthening Europe's R&I ecosystem by embedding sustainable Knowledge Valorisation practices. By enabling institutions to integrate IP and OS strategically, the project supports innovation, societal impact, and responsible research dissemination.

Future work will focus on submitting IP4OS work and experiences into the Knowledge Valorisation Platform for broader adoption, expanding multiplier networks, integrating the curriculum into institutional training programmes and European policies, and further engaging institutions, networks, and individuals to support knowledge valorisation across Europe via the IP4OS concept.

References

- (1) European Commission. (2025, September 19). EU valorisation policy. Research and Innovation. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy_en

(2) Alavi, M., Koch, P., MacDonald, L., Miller, K., Nilsonne, G., Priess-Buchheit, J. C., Scherer, J., Skoric, L., Stoev, P., Vrkic, D., Wyber, S., Yovcheva, N., & Yucebalkan, C. (2025). Unpacking the Possibilities of Intellectual Properties for Open Science. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.3897/arphapreprints.e181365>

(3) European Commission. (n.d.). EU valorisation policy. European Commission.

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy_en

(4) Miller, K., Hernando-Guzek, V., Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Fritz, C., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox:

FAIR-R²L Rubric. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231655>

(5) European Commission. (2023). Commission recommendation (EU) 2023/499 of 10 March 2023 on strengthening the European framework for knowledge valorisation [PDF]. EUR-Lex.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023H0499&from=EN>

(6) European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2023, March 1). Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/499 of 1 March 2023 on a Code of Practice on the management of intellectual assets for knowledge valorisation in the European Research Area, Publications Office of the European Union.

(7) Sharma, G., Alavi, M., Wyber, S., Baccigotti, A., Skoric, L., Papadopoulou, F., Miller, K., Priess-Buchheit, J. C., & Nilsonne, G. (2026). Synergy Framework for Knowledge Valorisation. Zenodo. [10.5281/zenodo.18683479](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18683479)

(8) Sharma, G., Alavi, M., Wyber, S., Baccigotti, A., Skoric, L., Papadopoulou, F., Miller, K., Priess-Buchheit, J. C., & Nilsonne, G. (2026). Synergy Framework for Knowledge Valorisation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18683480>

(9) Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Fritz, C., Hernando-Guzek, V., Miller, K., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox: Knowledge Valorisation Rubric. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18214839>

(10) GO FAIR Initiative. (n.d.). GO FAIR: Make your data & services FAIR. Retrieved February 22, 2026, from <https://www.go-fair.org/>

(11) Verhulst, S., Zahuranec, A. J., & Chafetz, H. (2025). Moving toward the FAIR-R principles: Advancing AI-ready data. SSRN. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5164337>

(12) Miller, K., Hernando-Guzek, V., Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Fritz, C., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox: FAIR-R²L Rubric. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18231655>

(13) Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Fritz, C., Hernando-Guzek, V., Miller, K., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox: Concepts, Valorisation Pathway, and Resources for IP and OS. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18223169>

(14) Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Fritz, C., Hernando-Guzek, V., Miller, K., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox: Valorisation Consultancy Form. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18232130>

(15) Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Fritz, C., Hernando-Guzek, V., Miller, K., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox: Guide on Multi-professional Teams and Consultations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18223173>

(16) Fritz, C., Alavi, M., Baccigotti, A., Čizmin, I., Hernando-Guzek, V., Miller, K., Skoric, L., Wyber, S., & Priess-Buchheit, J. C. (2026). IP4OS Toolbox: Pilot Learning Lab. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18224465>

(17) Priess-Buchheit, J. C., & Wyber, S. (2026). IP & OS — Managing Copyright and Licensing for Reuse. Profession Deepening Module on the Role of Librarians. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18620983>